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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Application of petiole and pedicel anatomy in plant taxonomy of five Solanaceae species from West Bengal, India

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Abstract

Here, five Solanaceous species were selected for a comparative study of the petiole and pedicel. A total of 28 characters were examined in the present investigation. The aim of this investigation was to determine the range of variation in these characters and identify taxonomically significant traits. Number of bundles in the vascular system of the petiole, Petiole shape and size, presence of spines, subsidiary vascular bundle size, trichome types with their number and position, vascular bundles shape and size, and wing characteristics were found to be taxonomically useful in distinguishing different species. Floral and fruit pedicel diameter, vascular bundle thickness, trichome types, and spine features also proved valuable in distinguishing species within the Solanaceae. In Past, there were very few works on the petiole and pedicel anatomy of Solanaceae with taxonomic application.

Keywords: Anatomy, Pedicel, Petiole, Solanaceae, Taxonomy, Trichome

Introduction

The family Solanaceae Juss., commonly known as the nightshade family, comprises 103 genera (POWO, 2025). Among the 103 genera, the type genus *Solanum* L. comprises 1,237 species, and is the largest genus within this family (POWO, 2025). *Datura* L. comprises 14 species, and *Physalis* L. comprises 94 species (POWO, 2025). Initially, Clarke, 1883 mentioned 27 *Solanum*, three *Datura*, and two *Physalis* species in the Flora of British India. In the more recent study, Kumari, 2004 reported 48 *Solanum*, four *Datura*, and eight *Physalis* species from India. Prain, 1903 in Bengal plants reported 11 *Solanum*, two *Datura*, and two *Physalis* species. Kalidass and Panda, 2019 reported 23 wild *Solanum* species with three cultivated *Solanum* species from the Eastern Ghat of India. Aubriot and Knapp, 2022 reported 51 spiny *Solanum* species from the major part of Asia. Gulaguli, et al. 2025 reported five *Datura* species from Karnataka, India. Among the five species, *Datura metel* includes three morphotypes.

Gómez-Nucamendi, et al. 2016 reported that leaf anatomical characters are helpful to distinguish four *Datura* species and a variety. Tovar and Giacomini, 2022 described a new species, *Solanum boshii* J.D. Tovar and reported that it differs from its morphologi-

cally similar species, *Solanum chlamydogynum* Bitter based on trichome morphology. Santos, et al. 2025 concluded that leaf anatomical studies are useful to separate taxa in the *Athenaea* sp. of Solanaceae.

Mbagwu, et al. 2024 studied the petiole anatomy of five species of the genus *Solanum* in Nigeria. Akinsulire, et al. 2018 found that petiole anatomy is taxonomically significant in *Terminalia*. Ekeke and Ogazie, 2020 found that petiole anatomy was taxonomically significant at both the genus and species levels in Asteraceae. Akhtar, et al. 2021 found that petiole anatomical characters were helpful in identifying asteraceous taxa from the Western Himalaya of Pakistan. Simon, et al. 2022 found that the anatomy of the tomato pedicel varies in relation to genotype. Nurit-Silva and Agra, 2011 concluded that leaf trichome morphology played an important role in distinguishing *Solanum* species.

For the present investigation, three species of *Solanum*- *Solanum nigrum* L., *Solanum sisymbriifolium* Lam., and *Solanum torvum* Sw.; one species of *Physalis* (*Physalis angulata* L.); and one species of *Datura* (*Datura metel* L.) were selected. In the past, a few research studies have explained the petiole anatomy of Solanaceae. Most experiments on the petiole anatomy are based on a single species of this family, and very few experiments are used in comparative studies on petiole anatomy among different species. Pedicel anatomy is very rarely considered in the field of taxonomy in Solanaceae. The present investigation aims to evaluate the taxonomic significance of petiole, flower pedicel, and fruit pedicel anatomy in the Solanaceae.

Materials and Methods

Plant samples were collected from various locations in Bankura and Burdwan districts of West Bengal (Tab. 1). For each species, three to five plant samples were collected from a single spot. Petioles from mature leaves, pedicels from mature flowers, and pedicels from mature, unripe fruits were selected for this investigation. Multiple samples of each species were preserved in FAA (formaldehyde, acetic acid, and alcohol). For anatomical study, freehand sections were prepared from the middle portion of the petiole and pedicel using a razor blade. For each species, at least five petioles, five flower pedicels and fruit pedicels were examined to assess the range of variation. Samples were stained using the safranin single-staining procedure. Each section was stained with 1 % safranin in 70% ethanol, then the excess stain was removed, and dehydration of the sample was done with the help of 70%, 90% and 95% ethanol. The samples were then mounted in glycerol to prepare semipermanent slides. Anatomical slides were studied and photographed under a Hoverlabs trilocular microscope attached with a 16 megapixel microscope camera.

For identification and authentication, various references, such as Bengal Plants and Flora of British India were consulted. Relevant protologues associated with the species names were also examined. Type materials available in various digital herbaria were examined (Tab. 1). Also, checked the present status of these species in POWO, 2025, Tropicos, 2025, and IPNI, 2025.

Table 1. Taxonomic study of five species and collection details of the present study.

Taxonomic details of five species under Solanaceae				Collection details of the present study	
Sl. No.	Name of the species with publication details	Collection related data	Original material	Collection area	Date
1	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L. in Species Plantarum. 1: 186.1753	Not mentioned	LINN 248.18!	Burdwan (23°15'13.3" N, 87°50'57.2" E)	21.07.2025
2	<i>Physalis angulata</i> L. in Species Plantarum. 1: 183.1753	Collected from India utraque	LINN 247.9!	Bankura (23°09'18.9" N, 87°36'30.4" E)	22.07.2025
3	<i>Solanum sisymbriifolium</i> Lam. in Tableau Encyclopedique et Methodique Des Trois Régnes De La Nature, Botanique. 2: 25. 1794	Collected by Commerson from Buenos Aires	LP011087!	Bankura (23°09'18.7" N, 87°36'29.5" E)	22.07.2025
4	<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw. in Nova Genera et species Plantarum seu Prodromus. 47. 1788	Collected by Olof Swartz from India Occidentalis	SR-5814!, S08-14102!, S08-14103!	Bankura (23°12'37.8" N, 87°36'36.9" E)	22.07.2025
5	<i>Datura metel</i> L. in Species Plantarum. 1: 179.1753	Habitat in Asia and Africa	BM000557992!	Bankura (23°09'25.3" N, 87°36'26.5" E)	23.07.2025

Results

The petiole connects the leaf blade to the plant, while the pedicel serves as a connective structure between the flower or fruit and the plant. In the present investigation, a total of 28 characters were examined in detail (Tab. 2). Petiole outlines are generally circular or oval with a flat to convex adaxial surface, and vascular bundles or vascular system shape are generally open, lunar-shaped except *S. torvum* and *D. metel* showing C or U shaped (Fig. 1. B, J, S, AG, AQ). Petiole thickness and breadth sometimes vary and may overlap, but the breadth of *S. torvum* is clearly distinct from the other species. Vascular bundles or vascular system contain three central bundles in *S. nigrum*, five to six in *Datura metel*, and the other three species contain three to four bundles. The vascular bundle of the petiole in *S. nigrum* is comparatively thinner than in the other species. The epidermal cells are generally oval to rectangular. In addition to the main vascular bundles, two subsidiary vascular bundles are present in all studied species, and *S. torvum* subsidiary vascular bundles are relatively larger among the five species (Fig. 1. B, E, J, M, S, T, AG, AH, AQ, AR). Winged petioles are characteristic of *S. nigrum* and *P. angulata* (Fig. 1. B, J). Spines are consistently present in the leaf petioles of *S. sisymbriifolium*, whereas in *S. torvum* they are variable, being present only occasionally (Fig. 1. U, AK). In leaf petiole, stellate trichomes occur only in *S. torvum*, whereas long glandular hairs (Stalk multicellular, head unicellular), partly gland-tipped branched hairs, and branchlet hairs occur only in *S. sisymbriifolium* (Fig. 1. T, AI). *S. nigrum* has finger hairs and short glandular hairs on the leaf petiole, with the adaxial surface bearing more hairs compared to the abaxial region (Fig. 1. B, D). Few hairs are present in *P. angulata* (Fig. 1. J, L). Only finger hair present in *D. metel* petiole (Fig. 1. AS). The smallest floral pedicel diameter is present in *S. nigrum*, and the largest in *D. metel* compared to others (Fig. 1. F, N, V, AL, AT). The floral pedicel cuticle of *S. nigrum* and *P. angulata* is thinner than that of *D. metel*. The vascular bundles of the floral pedicel are thicker in *D. metel* than in the other species (Fig. 1. F, N, O, V, W, AL, AM, AT, AU). The fruit pedicel diameter is comparatively larger in *D. metel* and *S. torvum* than in the other species (Fig. 1. G, P, AA, AN, AV). The vascular bundle thickness in *D. metel* is greater than in the other species (Fig. 1. G, H, P, Q, AA, AB, AN, AO, AV, AW). In the flower pedicel, stellate hairs with a gland tip are present only in *S. sisymbriifolium* (Fig. 1. V). A similar pattern was observed in the flower pedicel. Spines are present only in the flower and fruit pedicels of *S. sisymbriifolium* (Fig. 1. Z, AE).

Table 2. Comparative data of petiole and pedicel anatomy of five species under Solanaceae. (values are represented as “Average ± Standard Deviation (n values) (Minimum value-Maximum value)”.)

Sl. No.	Characters	<i>S. nigrum</i>	<i>P. angulata</i>	<i>S. sisymbriifolium</i>	<i>S. torvum</i>	<i>D. metel</i>
1	Petiole Outline	Circular and adaxial surface convex shape	Oval to circular and adaxial surface convex shape	Oval to circular and adaxial surface flat or slightly convex shape	Circular and adaxial surface flat or slightly concave	Circular and adaxial surface flat or slightly concave
2	Petiole thickness (µm)	1073.94 ± 57.33 (5) (1005.30-1149.63)	1578.41 ± 327.00 (5) (1027.43-1870.50)	2206.09 ± 464.50 (5) (1603.62-2764.48)	4104.05 ± 273.34 (5) (3744.91-4445.66)	2872.35 ± 634.84 (5) (2353.65-3943.06)
3	Petiole breadth (mid portion) (µm)	1171.85 ± 111.01 (5) (1056.21-1354.02)	1866.68 ± 390.68 (5) (1235.71-2309.18)	2261.61 ± 474.09 (5) (1620.41-2738.30)	4218.68 ± 233.75 (5) (3895.82-4509.73)	2823.39 ± 472.84 (5) (2337.05-3598.10)
4	Number of bundles in the vascular system of the petiole	3	3-4	3-4	3-4	5-6
5	Vascular bundles shape in petiole (µm)	Open arc and lunar shaped	Open arc and lunar shaped	Open arc and lunar shaped	Open arc and C or U shaped	Open arc and C or U shaped
6	Vascular bundles thickness in petiole (µm)	225.88 ± 15.98 (5) (213.44-252.55)	382.81 ± 119.64 (5) (205.62-507.72)	429.54 ± 127.72 (5) (258.16-555.29)	662.15 ± 62.00 (5) (578.42-725.78)	451.85 ± 115.06 (5) (317.07-618.33)
7	Vascular bundles breadth in petiole (µm)	843.59 ± 99.61 (5) (733.41-1002.97)	1234.29 ± 294.95 (5) (772.77-1596.87)	1422.38 ± 342.61 (5) (902.52-1772.10)	2465.57 ± 191.47 (5) (2206.34-2679.91)	1958.91 ± 315.89 (5) (1585.91-2410.35)
8	Petiole winged or not	Winged	Winged	Absent	Absent	Absent
9	Spine in petiole	Absent	Absent	Present	Generally absent sometimes present	Absent
10	Cuticle thickness in petiole (µm)	2.50 ± 0.80 (5) (1.52-3.40)	3.36 ± 0.91 (5) (2.15-4.45)	6.34 ± 1.32 (5) (4.59-7.77)	4.87 ± 1.64 (5) (2.75-6.54)	3.98 ± 0.75 (5) (3.12-5.16)
11	Epidermal cell shape in petiole	Oval to rectangular	Oval to rectangular	Oval to rectangular	Oval to rectangular	Oval to rectangular

12	Adaxial epidermal cell thickness in petiole (μm)	18.10 \pm 3.11 (5) (14.37-21.59)	25.88 \pm 3.02 (5) (23.69-31.15)	20.99 \pm 4.10 (5) (17.43-27.75)	22.51 \pm 4.34 (5) (15.73-27.10)	21.28 \pm 2.90 (5) (17.79-24.07)
13	Adaxial epidermal cell breadth in petiole (μm)	20.26 \pm 3.14 (5) (14.85-22.88)	30.84 \pm 9.21 (5) (22.53-46.26)	25.34 \pm 4.37 (5) (21.77-31.20)	27.97 \pm 1.85 (5) (25.67-30.63)	23.84 \pm 7.15 (5) (15.01-31.97)
14	Abaxial epidermal cell thickness in petiole (μm)	24.94 \pm 4.38 (5) (17.91-29.23)	33.39 \pm 4.91 (5) (28.64-41.67)	24.76 \pm 5.67 (5) (16.98-31.28)	29.84 \pm 4.09 (5) (23.63-35.06)	27.55 \pm 3.20 (5) (24.10-31.55)
15	Abaxial epidermal cell breadth in petiole (μm)	27.02 \pm 6.36 (5) (18.29-35.99)	41.86 \pm 9.61 (5) (32.32-57.51)	33.65 \pm 2.23 (5) (30.77-36.30)	35.59 \pm 6.10 (5) (26.89-41.68)	21.20 \pm 3.07 (5) (16.00-23.86)
16	Subsidiary vascular bundle thickness in petiole (μm)	69.92 \pm 13.60 (5) (55.92-83.90)	113.01 \pm 29.21 (5) (64.94-144.17)	213.22 \pm 80.29 (5) (88.45-286.97)	385.12 \pm 109.24 (5) (259.02-559.66)	115.27 \pm 25.89 (5) (95.03-159.61)
17	Subsidiary vascular bundle breadth in petiole (μm)	63.68 \pm 16.87 (5) (39.84-82.85)	94.82 \pm 18.40 (5) (62.45-108.60)	188.76 \pm 77.57 (5) (85.51-267.31)	282.21 \pm 64.31 (5) (211.68-359.78)	94.65 \pm 31.51 (5) (68.17-141.43)
18	Trichome types in petiole	Finger hair present (cells 2 to 5), Short glandular hair very rarely (unicellular stalk and multicellular head), less number of hairs on the abaxial surface.	Finger hair very rarely present (cells 2 to 3)	Long glandular hair (Stalk multi cell, head single cell), finger hair (cells 1 to 3), partly gland-tipped branched hair, branchlet hair	Stellate hair	Finger hair (cells 2 to 4)
19	Floral pedicel diameter (μm)	355.24 \pm 43.73 (5) (305.47-412.20)	498.12 \pm 58.51 (5) (457.84-600.21)	674.81 \pm 85.55 (5) (550.85-787.33)	754.63 \pm 84.31 (5) (644.15-830.99)	3098.33 \pm 206.15 (5) (2847.96-3366.32)
20	Floral pedicel Vascular Bundle thickness (μm)	61.41 \pm 11.64 (5) (47.98-80.07)	74.50 \pm 12.79 (5) (61.13-90.47)	109.89 \pm 27.73 (5) (77.70-150.63)	90.04 \pm 6.39 (5) (80.81-96.08)	428.04 \pm 31.99 (5) (400.85-479.46)
21	Floral pedicel cuticle thickness (μm)	1.57 \pm 0.41 (5) (1.10-2.07)	2.22 \pm 0.33 (5) (1.86-2.59)	3.66 \pm 1.29 (5) (1.72-5.28)	3.07 \pm 0.70 (5) (1.85-3.57)	3.53 \pm 0.42 (5) (2.87-4.01)
22	Trichome types in the floral pedicel	Finger hair very rarely present (cells 1 to 4), Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)	Finger hair very rarely present (2 celled), Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)	Long glandular hair (Stalk multi cell, head single cell), Stellate hair with glandule, finger hair (cells 1 to 3), partly gland-tipped branched hair, branchlet hair, Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)	Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head), long glandular hair (Stalk multicelled)	Finger hair present (cells 1 to 4), very rarely Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)
23	Spine in floral pedicel	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent
24	Fruit pedicel diameter (μm)	580.61 \pm 80.92 (5) (506.02-699.86)	646.33 \pm 62.23 (5) (577.31-745.84)	1222.21 \pm 138.36 (5) (994.68-1327.06)	1490.52 \pm 165.75 (5) (1311.19-1748.04)	3693.26 \pm 323.29 (5) (3439.19-4250.72)
25	Fruit pedicel Vascular Bundle thickness (μm)	118.37 \pm 7.97 (5) (108.95-125.49)	124.46 \pm 34.45 (5) (84.99-167.69)	289.39 \pm 44.42 (5) (237.91-335.02)	286.09 \pm 11.92 (5) (266.89-297.67)	561.29 \pm 141.80 (5) (426.62-788.44)
26	Fruit pedicel cuticle thickness (μm)	2.19 \pm 0.65 (5) (1.47-3.08)	3.19 \pm 1.18 (5) (1.90-5.08)	6.99 \pm 0.84 (5) (5.56-7.66)	3.81 \pm 1.42 (5) (2.52-6.19)	4.90 \pm 2.28 (5) (2.53-8.15)
27	Trichome types in fruit pedicel	Finger hair very rarely present (cells 1 to 4), Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)	Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head) hair very rare	Long glandular hair (Stalk multi cell, head single cell), Stellate hair with glandule, finger hair (cells 1 to 2), partly gland-tipped branched hair, branchlet hair, Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head), gland-tipped branched hair	Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head), long glandular hair (Stalk multicelled)	Finger hair very rarely present (cells 2 to 3), very rarely Short glandular hair (unicellular stalk and multicellular head)
28	Spine in fruit pedicel	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent

Figure 1. Habit, petiole anatomy and pedicel anatomy. A. Habit of *S. nigrum*, B-E. Petiole anatomy of *S. nigrum*, F. Pedicel anatomy of *S. nigrum* flower, G-H. Pedicel anatomy of *S. nigrum* fruit. I. Habit of *P. angulata*, J-M. Petiole anatomy of *P. angulata* flower, N-O. Pedicel anatomy of *P. angulata* flower, P-Q. Pedicel anatomy of *P. angulata* fruit. R. Habit of *S. sisymbriifolium*, S-T. Petiole anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium*, U. Petiole anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium* spine region, V-Y pedicel anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium* flower, Z. Pedicel anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium* flower spine region, AA-AD. Pedicel anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium* fruit, AE. pedicel anatomy of *S. sisymbriifolium* fruit spine region. AF. Habit of *S. torvum*, AG-AJ. Petiole anatomy of *S. torvum*, AK. Petiole anatomy of *S. torvum* spine region, AL-AM. pedicel anatomy of *S. torvum* flower, AN-AO. pedicel anatomy of *S. torvum* fruit, AP. Habit of *D. metel*, AQ-AS. Petiole anatomy of *D. metel*, AT-AU. pedicel anatomy of *D. metel* flower, AV-AX. Pedicel anatomy of *D. metel* fruit. Note: WI: Wing; VB: Vascular Bundle; SVB: Subsidiary Vascular Bundle; SGH: Short Glandular Hair; FH: Finger Hair; LGH: Long Glandular Hair; GSH: Stellate hair with a gland tip; BH: Branchlet Hair; GBH: Gland-tipped Branched Hair; PGBH: Partly Gland-tipped Branched Hair; SH: Stellate Hair.

Discussion

A very primitive-level taxonomic review was required for the identification of selected material. The most popular and confusing synonym of *P. angulata* is *P. minima*. Linnaeus, 1753 published the names *P. minima* L. and *P. angulata* L. in Species Plantarum, but POWO, 2025 treated *P. minima* as a synonym of *P. angulata* and *P. angulata* as an accepted name. Another popular name, *Datura fastuosa* L., is the synonym of *D. metel* (POWO, 2025). Ekeke and Ogazie, 2020 reported that the number of accessory vascular bundles in Asteraceae petioles varied. The present study showed that the number of accessory vascular bundles or subsidiary vascular bundles is constant (i.e., two), but their size is highly variable. They also mentioned that the sizes of the vascular bundles were quite different. The present study shows that vascular bundle size differs not only in the petiole but also in the pedicel, which is also helpful for identification. Mbagwu, et al. 2024 reported that petiole shape could be Semicircle, oval or triangular-semicircle, and petiole vascular bundle shape could vary as arc, U, or V shape. The present investigation shows that the petiole shape is circular or oval with a flat to convex adaxial surface, and vascular bundles arc or lunar, or sometimes C or U shaped. Akinsulire, et al. 2018 mentioned that the shape and arrangement of vascular bundles play a good role in classifying five taxa under *Terminalia*. The present work shows that the vascular system of *D. metel* is different to the other four taxa, which helps in identification. Akhtar, et al. 2021 used wing character in their study on Asteraceae and found wings present in some species others without wings. The Present study shows that among the five species, only *S. nigrum* and *P. angulata* have wings. Wahua and Nkomadu, 2017 reported that bicollateral vascular bundles are present in the *D. metel* petiole. The present investigation supports this, as *D. metel* petiole vascular bundles are of the bicollateral type with two subsidiary vascular bundles. Bhat, et al. 2018 found U-shaped bicollateral type vascular bundle and two additional traces in the lateral wings of the petiole of *P. angulata*. Present research shows lunar-shaped vascular bundle with two subsidiary vascular bundles in the wings. They also mentioned trichomes are absent. But the present investigation shows finger hairs present, but very rare. Al-Hadeethi, et al. 2021 found an ovate-shaped petiole with two lateral sides, average cuticle thickness 1.5 μm , unicellular and uniseriate trichome, and average epidermis thickness 16.5 μm in *S. nigrum*. The present work shows a circular petiole and a convex-shaped adaxial surface with two lateral wings, cuticle thickness varies from 1.52 μm to 3.40 μm , with an average of 2.50 μm , adaxial epidermal cell thickness varies from 14.85 μm to 22.88 μm , with an average of 20.26 μm , and abaxial epidermal cell thickness varies from 18.29 μm to 35.99 μm , with an average of 27.02 μm . Nurit-Silva, et al. 2011 reported that the petiole anatomy of *S. torvum* is a circular outline, bicollateral vascularization, three to four central bundles, U shape, and two accessory bundles. The present study supports this previous investigation. Rančić, et al. 2010 studied the anatomy of *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Tomato) of the Solanaceae fruit petiole, and reported presence of cuticle on epidermal cells with long multicellular nonglandular hair and glandular trichome. Present research shows the presence of cuticle on pedicel epidermis and different types of hair.

Ahmad, 1964 reported short glandular hair with a 1-celled stalk with a multicelled head, long two to four cells stalk glandular hair with 1 to multi-celled head and nonglandular hair three to five celled, uniseriate and simple in the leaf of *D. metel*. The present study shows the presence of short glandular hair with nonglandular hair in the pedicel and only nonglandular hair in the petiole of *D. metel*. Non-glandular hair cell numbers vary from one to four. Ahmad, 1964 also reports short glandular hair, and nonglandular hair one to multi-celled, uniseriate and simple in the leaf of *S. nigrum*. Present studies show 2 to 5 celled finger hair in the petiole, whereas one to four celled finger hair in the pedicel, and short glandular hair present in both the petiole and pedicel. Seithe and Anderson, 1982, Seithe and Sullivan, 1990 reported different types of hairs in a single species; our studies also support this. Seithe and Sullivan, 1990 found only a few hairs in *P. angulata*, the present study shows the same character in the petiole and pedicel. Sumitha and Thankappan, 2018 found stellate hair in *S. nigrum* and *S. torvum* in foliar epidermis. The Present study shows that in the case of petiole stellate hair only present in *S. torvum*. Huang, et al. 2023 found phylogenetic analysis shows *Solanum* is closer to *Physalis* not *Datura*. Anatomical data of pedicel and petiole from the present analysis show that *S. nigrum* shares some characteristics with *P. angulata*.

Conclusion

Among the five species of *Solanaceae*, the number of bundles in the vascular system of the petiole, petiole shape, petiole size, vascular bundles shape, size, wing character, subsidiary vascular bundle size, presence of spine and trichome types are helpful to distinguish. However, the present study shows that these characters are not always genus-specific but are useful at the species level. For example, wing characters are not genus-specific when comparing *S. nigrum* and *P. angulata*, but they show significant differences between *D. metel* and *P. angulata*. Furthermore, wing characters are not present in all species of *Solanum*. The number of hairs is less in *P. angulata* and *Datura metel*, with only two types of hair, i.e. finger hair and short glandular hair. Some trichome characters are highly

species-specific, such as stellate trichomes in *S. torvum*, and partly gland-tipped branched hairs and branchlet hairs found only in *S. sisymbriifolium*. Floral and fruit pedicel diameter, vascular bundle thickness, trichome types, and spine characters also help distinguish different species. Rather than relying on a single character, the combination of multiple characters is taxonomically stronger and more significant for distinguishing species. To fulfill the detailed study on the global Solanaceae, a phylogenetic relationship with a detailed morphoanatomical study including pedicel and petiole anatomy, trichome diversity will be required in future.

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